

Diseases of dryland rice in Mato Grosso, Brazil, 1981.

Site	Variety	Blast		Narrow brown leaf spot	Scald	Stack burn	Sheath blight	Sheath rot	Glume blotch	Brown spot
		Foliar	Neck							
<i>Cuiaba</i>										
Umurama Farm	IAC 47	Severe	Severe (20-30%)	Severe	-	-	-	Mild	Moderate	Trace
Prata Farm	IAC 47 ^a IAC 25 IAC 164	Trace	Severe (20%)	-	Severe	-	-	Mild	-	-
Rondonopolis	Uniform Variety Trial, 18 entries	Trace	-	Mild	Moderate to severe	Moderate to severe	-	Moderate to severe	Moderate to severe	Mild
<i>Jaciara</i>										
Guarita Farm	IAC 47	-	Mild	Very severe (neck region affected)	Trace	-	-	Moderate	-	-
Expt. fields	UVT, 18 entries	Trace	Mild	-	Moderate	-	-	Moderate	-	-
Santa Fe Exp. Station EMPA	IAC 25 ^b	-	-	-	-	Moderate	-	-	Moderate	-
Chapada dos Guimaraes										
Estrella do Norte	IAC 47 ^c		Trace to mild	Moderate to severe (neck region affected)	Mild	-	Mild	Mild	Trace	Mild

^aDisease severe at early growth stage. ^bSprayed twice with BIM '75PM fungicide. ^cSprayed with Kitazin.

tivation — IAC 47, IAC 25, and IAC 164 — are highly susceptible to the fungal diseases observed.

- The incidence of one or more diseases was high at every site.
- Narrow brown leaf spot disease was found on the neck node, giving an appearance of neck blast, a symptom which so far has not been noticed in Asian countries.
- Typical white chaffy panicles due to neck blast were not observed, although some farms had a high

incidence — more than 20% — of neck infection, probably because of late infection.

- Spraying with tricyclalole [5-methyl-1, 2, 3-triazol (3,4-b)- benzo-thiazol] helped control blast but not stack burn.
- Most of the fungal diseases observed are known to be seed-borne. In many areas rice cultivation started in the last two to three years. Apparently, the diseases were introduced through seed and estab-

lished because of favorable weather conditions.

- No bacterial or viral diseases of rice were observed.

In the absence of disease-resistant varieties suitable for Brazilian conditions, the interim measures to minimize diseases are regular seed treatment with systemic fungicides, spraying the crop three times with fungicides having different active ingredients in rotation, and producing disease-free seed through plant protection. ■

Dose and application schedule of IBP granules to control rice blast

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Rice neck blast (*Pyricularia oryzae* Cav.) causes yield losses in transplanted paddy of valleys and foothills of Nagaland. Abundant rainfall from April to October reduces the efficacy of spray fungicides. Earlier experiments showed that IBP (0,0 - Diisopropyl - S-benzyl

thiophosphate (IBP) 10% G) granule was the most effective fungicide to control blast.

This experiment in 1980 kharif investigated the effect and cost of an application schedule of IBP granules.

Six doses of IBP granules were dispersed by hand between rows in two equal applications (at tillering and at panicle initiation). Standing water (5-6 cm) in the paddy was maintained for 6-7 days. All treatments gave significant neck blast control (see table). IBP granules at 3.74 kg a.i./ha was the most economical dosage (yield 19.24% more

than control). Higher doses of IBP granules gave better neck blast control but without significant increases in yield. ■

IBP granule effect on neck blast incidence and grain yield of IR8 at Nagaland, India.

IBP granules (kg a.i./ha)	Neck blast infection (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
2.50	35.4	3.96
3.74	37.1	4.40
5.00	32.7	3.81
6.24	28.8	4.28
7.50	25.6	4.04
8.74	31.9	4.08
0 (control)	52.3	3.69
CD at 5%		0.36